

Freedom and Bondage: An Interpretation of the Concept of Freedom in *Middlemarch*

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Abstract:

George Eliot, a renowned female writer and philosopher of the Victorian era, significantly embodied her philosophical ideas within her novels. The characters in *Middlemarch* relentlessly pursue freedom amidst the constraints of human nature, legal frameworks, and personal desires. This paper posits a remarkable resonance between George Eliot's concept of freedom in *Middlemarch* and Baruch de Spinoza's interpretation of freedom in his philosophical work, *Ethica*. However, Eliot's creation of *Middlemarch* was not intended to serve as a vehicle for Spinoza's view of freedom. Spinoza's concept of

freedom provided solid theoretical support for Eliot's literary creation, and based on this, Eliot deepened the concept of freedom within *Middlemarch*, demonstrating her profound understanding and development of Spinoza's ideas. Furthermore, this paper also reveals the complex societal issues and sharp human contradictions highlighted in the characters' pursuits of freedom in *Middlemarch*. By analyzing Eliot's thoughts on freedom and examining the influence of Spinoza's view of freedom on her creation, this paper aims to open up a new path to help readers gain a more comprehensive grasp of Eliot's philosophical ideas and the implications embedded within her literary oeuvre.

Keywords: *Middlemarch*, George Eliot, freedom, Baruch de Spinoza, *Ethics*.

Introduction

George Eliot (1819-1880), originally named Mary Ann Evans, possessed remarkable linguistic talents that laid a solid foundation for her development in literature. She translated many works with broad philosophical implications, including D. F. Strauss' *The Life of Jesus, Critically Examined* (1835-1836), Ludwig Andreas Feuerbach's *Essence of Christianity* (1841), and Baruch de Spinoza's *Tractatus Theologico-Politicus* (1670) and *Ethica* (1677). These translation works not only enriched her knowledge and philosophical system but also

had a profound impact on her ethical thinking. Before she emerged as a renowned novelist, Eliot's final academic pursuit centered on translating Spinoza's *Ethica*. As early as 1856, she completed the English translation of *Ethica* and named it *Ethics*.

Ethics, at the heart of Spinoza's philosophy, contains various significant ideas, particularly his view of freedom. According to the German poet Heinrich Heine (1985: 70), "All our present-day philosophers, possibly without knowing it, look through glasses that Baruch Spinoza ground". Drawing on the ideas of his predecessors,

Spinoza articulated a nuanced understanding of freedom centered on human happiness and liberty, laying the foundation for subsequent developments in the concept of freedom. He defined it as anything which “exists solely by the necessity of its nature and is determined to act by itself alone” (Spinoza, 2020: 74). The intellectual love towards God is the supreme manifestation of freedom. In addition, he systematically explored the realization of human freedom, emphasizing that human freedom is inextricably linked to the understanding and observance of natural necessity, adherence to laws, and rational control of one’s emotions. Spinoza further posited that reason and virtue are the paths to freedom, requiring individuals to acquire true knowledge of necessity through reason, transform it into their necessity, and abide by reason and virtue to ultimately achieve true freedom. In his view, a free man is guided by reason, loves and respects nature, maintains harmony within themselves and others, and abides by laws.

As the pioneering translator of Spinoza’s *Ethica* into English, George Eliot not only strove to disseminate Spinoza’s conception of freedom to a wider readership, but also ingeniously infused her reflections on freedom into every aspect of characterization, plotting, and thematic exploration in her novels. Her widely acclaimed novel *Middlemarch* (1872) is frequently regarded as a fictional representation of Spinoza’s *Ethics* (Henson, 2009: 18). Although some scholars have explored the connection between Spinoza and Eliot (Clare, 2020; Guo, 2021; Mao, 2024), their studies mostly focus on the influence of Spinoza’s emotional, moral, and religious ideas on Eliot. In contrast, research on how Spinoza’s concept of freedom influenced Eliot’s novel writing remains relatively underdeveloped.

To fill this gap, this paper will focus on how characters in *Middlemarch* strive for freedom and self-realization in the face of the limitations of human nature, moral and legal constraints, and the enslavement of personal desires, as well as the social issues and contradictions of human nature exposed in their pursuits of freedom. The analysis will offer readers a more holistic interpretive lens into the connotations of Eliot’s

works and how she both inherited and advanced Spinoza’s concept of freedom within her literary realm.

Freedom and Human Nature in *Middlemarch*

Spinoza, a determinist philosopher, asserted that humans are “a part of Nature” and “can never bring ourselves to a state in which we should want nothing external to preserve our existence, or so live as to have no commerce with things outside ourselves” (2020: 240). As a result, man must abide by the general laws of nature and accept the constraints exerted by external natural forces. Simultaneously, Spinoza emphasized that man is a “rational animal” capable of recognizing natural necessity through reason, intuition, and deduction. When individuals transform the external necessity of nature into their inner necessity and act accordingly, they transform what was once coercive activity into voluntary and desired action, thereby achieving freedom. George Eliot was deeply influenced by Spinoza’s conception of freedom. In *Middlemarch*, she underscores the pivotal role of adhering to the necessity of nature in achieving personal freedom through the portrayal of Celia Brooke’s and Dorothea Brooke’s quests for freedom amidst the constraints of natural laws.

1. Celia Brooke: Conforming to Human Nature

In *Middlemarch*, contrary to the idealistic Dorothea Brooke, Celia accepts her fate and conforms to the laws of nature, which is reflected in her behavior that meets the common demands of wealthy women in the Victorian era, particularly in her aesthetic preferences and marital beliefs.

The attire of wealthy women reflected the fashion taste and aesthetic values of the upper class in the Victorian era. Their clothing is often delicate and they always use a variety of fine accessories to embellish their outfits, such as pearl necklaces, gemstone earrings, lace gloves, and so on, which reflect their social status and wealth. “The Brooke connections, though not

exactly aristocratic, were unquestionably ‘good’” (Eliot, 2000: 5). Therefore, in terms of aesthetic preferences, despite Celia and Dorothea living in the countryside, where ostentation was not to be practiced under the influence of religion, Celia only superficially adhered to the austere fashion but maintained a deep love for dressing as a wealthy Victorian lady. Although she “wore scarcely more trimmings” (ibid), upon closer inspection, it is not difficult to notice that “her dress differed from her sister’s and had a shade of coquetry in its arrangements” (ibid). Her hairstyle, resembling the Henrietta-Maria style, also demonstrates her pursuit of fashion.

Additionally, when informed that their mother had left them some jewelry, unlike Dorothea’s indifference, Celia could not wait to ask Dorothea to distribute the jewels when their Uncle, Mr. Brooke, gave the jewels to Dorothea for “exactly six months”, arguing that “to put them by and take no notice of them” (Eliot, 2000: 8) is a sign of disrespect to their mother. Celia even used the example of the devout Christian Madame Poincon, who often wears ornaments, to persuade Dorothea that even Christians can adorn themselves. When Dorothea fastened a necklace of purple amethysts around Celia’s neck, Celia tried not to smile with pleasure. But when Dorothea kept the emerald ring and bracelet for herself, Celia felt displeased, believing that the “emeralds would suit her complexion even better than purple amethysts” (Eliot, 2000: 9) and asking Dorothea if she would wear the jewelry in public. These details vividly illustrate Celia’s love for dressing, aligned with the Victorian era’s emphasis on feminine adornment.

Furthermore, it is widely acknowledged that marriage in the Victorian era held a dual significance for women. It served as both an emotional home and a pivotal means of enhancing their social status. Consequently, selecting a partner who could offer material and social support was paramount for Victorian women. In terms of marital beliefs, Celia also conformed to the Victorian era’s perspective on women’s marriage. Instead of blindly pursuing romantic love, she chose to marry Sir James Chettam, a man of commensurate age and status,

jointly assuming family responsibilities and facing life’s challenges. Their marital life was peaceful and happy, culminating in the birth of their son, Arthur. This pragmatic and rational approach enables Celia to achieve the personal freedom akin to what Spinoza envisioned. Celia’s character and choices not only align with the social backdrop of the Victorian era but also embody the universal wisdom of humans conforming to the necessities of nature. Moreover, her image provides a valuable perspective for readers to understand women’s status and choices in that era.

2. Dorothea Brooke: Opposing to Human Nature

In *Middlemarch*, the portrayal of the failed marriage between the heroine Dorothea Brooke and Edward Casaubon deeply reflects George Eliot’s meditation on the tragic consequences of disobeying natural necessity. Dorothea, the “Saint Theresa” with passion and vigor, devout religious beliefs, and lofty ambitions, rejected the confining life of a typical middle-class woman and pursued an epic life. She detested extravagant jewelry and horse riding, instead devoting herself to public causes, designing houses for tenant farmers, and worrying over the plight of the poor. Nevertheless, her actions have not been recognized by society.

More crucially, Dorothea’s understanding of marriage and choice of partner was incompatible with the prevailing Victorian notions, which upheld a matchmaking ideology centered on compatibility in age, social background, and even worldview. However, to Dorothea, love is a process of self-improvement through the development of one’s emotional understanding. Having lost their parents at a young age, Dorothea and Celia have received a superficial home education in both English and Swiss households, which are far from sufficient to satisfy a curious child. Moreover, Dorothea is a devout believer, has read many religious works, and is inquisitive about philosophy and religion. Consequently, at first, she held a lofty belief in love, hoping that marriage “would deliver her from her girlish subjection to her ignorance, and take her along the grandest path” (Eliot, 2000:

19). She disregarded genteel suitors, yearning instead for a great man like Milton as a lifelong companion. When the much older Casaubon entered her life, and she learned that he was compiling the “Key to all Mythologies”, Dorothea saw in him the fulfillment of her ideals. In her eyes, this pseudo-scholar was akin to the “living Bossuet” and “modern Augustine”. Thus, although all around her were against the marriage, Mr. Brooke and Celia repeatedly tried to dissuade her from marrying Casaubon, and Sir James even described Casaubon as “no better than a mummy” and pointed out that “he has one foot in the grave” (Eliot, 2000: 37), Dorothea remained obstinate, dismissing their opinions as mundane prejudices. She unhesitatingly married Casaubon, thrilled at the prospect of collaborating with him on a monumental theological work and fulfilling her own life’s purpose.

However, her choice did not bring the expected happiness but instead plunged her into deeper pain. She longed to enter Casaubon’s inner world, sharing his sorrows and troubles, but he married her solely for “adorning his life with the graces of female companionship”, and “irradiating the gloom which fatigue was apt to hang over the intervals of studious labor with the play of female fancy” (Eliot, 2000: 40). What he needs is a nurse and devoted listener, not an assistant. During their honeymoon in Rome, Dorothea was abandoned amidst the ruins and palaces of ancient Rome, and she seemed to have a vague sense that her dreams had been shattered. Upon returning to Lowick Manor, she even realized that her husband lacked genuine scholarship and was eccentric and stubborn. She could not be his assistant or spiritual partner in completing his masterpiece and was instead subjected to his selfish and narrow-minded suspicions. Her ideal marriage became a cage, her dreams were cruelly shattered, and her freedom was brutally stripped away. Ultimately, their marriage ended in tragedy.

Through the portrayal of Dorothea’s tragic marriage to Casaubon, Eliot echoes Spinoza’s views, emphasizing the importance of adhering to human nature to achieve personal freedom. According to their definition of individual

freedom, Dorothea exhibits the utmost passive state in this marriage.

Freedom and Legal Provisions in *Middlemarch*

When considering human freedom from the perspective of man and society, Spinoza asserted that “man is a social animal” (Spinoza, 2020: 250) who cannot endure solitary existence. He also believed that “men will nevertheless experience that by mutual aid they will procure the things they want much more easily, and that by united powers only can they avoid perils which everywhere threaten them” (ibid). Furthermore, he emphasized that the purpose of the state is to guarantee the freedom of its citizens, and “it will thus have the power of prescribing the common rule of life and of improving laws” (Spinoza, 2020: 254). Spinoza extended the concept of natural law to that of national law, arguing that the laws of the freest state should be based on reason. By following the guidance of reason and living by legal provisions, people can be protected by them, acting in harmony with the necessity of their nature and thereby achieving freedom.

In *Middlemarch*, George Eliot delved into how national laws and professional ethics impact individual freedom by describing the social customs and interpersonal relationships in the small town. She firmly believed that reasonable and just national laws, along with strict professional ethical norms, not only maintain social stability but also provide a safeguard for the realization of individual freedom.

1. Nicholas Bulstrode: Breaching Legal Provisions

Through detailed descriptions, Eliot vividly illustrated how the banker Nicholas Bulstrode, in his pursuit of profit, gradually crossed the red line of the law and ultimately fell into an untenable situation. In chapter 61 of the novel, Eliot reveals Bulstrode’s transgressions against national laws and social ethics through his dialogue with Will Ladislaw. In his early years, Bulstrode, a bank clerk, became an accountant through the esteem of Will’s grandfather, Mr.

Dunkirk. After Mr. Dunkirk's death, he married Mrs. Dunkirk by concealing the truth that Will's mother, Sarah Dunkirk, was still alive, thus seizing the family's wealth and gaining respect and recognition for his fortune and status. He enjoyed the benefits of his unethical and illegal behaviors while confessing his sins to God. When threatened by John Raffles with his past misdeeds, Bulstrode, though frightened, worried not about "legal punishment or of beggary" (Eliot, 2000: 380), but about "seeing disclosed to the judgment of his neighbors and the mournful perception of his wife certain facts of his past life which would render him an object of scorn and an opprobrium of the religion with which he had diligently associated himself" (ibid). Consequently, when Raffles was seriously ill and living at the Stone Court, Bulstrode deliberately concealed from Nurse Mrs. Abel the doctor's instructions not to allow Raffles to drink alcohol or overdose on opium, leading to a sudden deterioration and eventual death of Raffles. His past sins, however, were eventually revealed and spread, stripping him of his cherished reputation, rendering him an object of scorn, and alienating him from true freedom.

Through the characterization of Bulstrode, Eliot reveals a prevalent phenomenon in society at that time: in the frenzied pursuit of success and wealth, people often easily overstep the boundaries of morality and law. This revelation not only enables readers to have a deeper understanding of the social reality at that time but also triggers their in-depth reflection and discussion on moral concepts, legal norms, and social responsibility.

2. Tertius Lydgate: Violating Medical Ethics and Laws

Drawing upon Spinoza's assertion of the inseparable bond between law and freedom, George Eliot, in *Middlemarch*, underscored the indispensability of professional ethics and laws for personal liberty through the intricate narrative of the protagonist, Dr. Tertius Lydgate, who violated medical ethics and became embroiled in Bulstrode's "murder" case.

Lydgate is a young doctor with wide knowledge and advanced ideas, sharing idealistic traits with

Dorothea. He aspired to elevate the medical standards of Middlemarch and advance the town's medical cause through his efforts. However, some of his experimental practices transgressed medical ethics. A notable instance is his involvement in the auctioneer Mr. Borthrop Trumbull's clinical expectant theory experiment on pneumonia. This theory involves "watching the course of an interesting disease when left as much as possible to itself, so that the stages might be noted for future guidance" (Eliot, 2000: 279). Mr. Trumbull, being robust, serves as an ideal subject. Therefore, to persuade him to participate in the experiment and cooperate in documenting the changes for future clinical reference, Lydgate expended considerable effort, explaining the principles and processes of the experiment at length, assuring that medical personnel would closely monitor his disease's progression. Furthermore, knowing Trumbull's vanity, Lydgate intentionally "indulged him with a little technical talk" (Eliot, 2000: 280), outlining the various benefits of participating, such as "offering a beautiful example of a disease with all its phases seen in clear delineation, and that he probably had the rare strength of mind voluntarily to become the test of a rational procedure, and thus make the disorder of his pulmonary functions a general benefit to society" (ibid). Nevertheless, he remained silent about the potential risks inherent in the experiment.

Pneumonia was an acute illness at that time, and even today, with advanced medical conditions, improper or untimely treatment can lead to dire consequences. Therefore, Lydgate experimented without informing the subject of the potentially severe consequences undoubtedly violates the patient's right to know and autonomy, as well as medical ethics. This action, to a certain extent, foretells his ultimate failure to succeed in his medical career.

In addition, the marriage of Lydgate and Rosamond Vincy marked a turning point in Lydgate's fortune. Upon his arrival in Middlemarch, Lydgate was captivated by the beauty of Rosamond, the eldest daughter of the mayor, and the two quickly fell in love and married. However, married life did not meet

Lydgate's expectations. Rosamond's extravagant spending habits rapidly deteriorated their financial situation, leading to a mountain of debts. Therefore, Lydgate was forced to consider selling their belongings and moving out of their luxurious residence, even affecting his beloved scientific research. Additionally, in desperation to resolve their financial woes, he sought assistance from Bulstrode. Initially, Bulstrode not only rejected Lydgate's request for a loan but also informed Lydgate that he would terminate his sponsorship of the new fever hospital. However, when Bulstrode learned from Caleb Garth that the ill Raffles was residing in the Stone Court, he offered to lend Lydgate 1,000 pounds to bribe him. Unaware of the truth, Lydgate was deeply grateful to Bulstrode. Nevertheless, it was this very 1,000 pounds that embroiled Lydgate in Bulstrode's "murder" of Raffles, landing him in a situation where he was despised by the town's residents. Ultimately, Lydgate chose to abandon his medical ideals and departed for London to pursue his medical career. However, the whims of fate did not end there, as he tragically ended his life at the young age of 50. Through Lydgate's tragic ending, George Eliot profoundly reveals the devastating impact of violating laws and professional ethics on personal freedom, complementing Spinoza's perspective on freedom from a human-nature angle.

Freedom and Reason in *Middlemarch*

On the level of man and self, Spinoza believed that emotion is the inherent characteristic of human nature, capable of increasing or diminishing, assisting or restraining the power of bodily and mental activities (Spinoza, 2020: 163). However, as part of nature, humans often find themselves governed by emotion. If a man is solely driven by emotion, he tends to be arbitrary in the process of pursuing freedom, truth, goodness, and beauty. Moreover, he easily becomes the plaything of his desires and evil thoughts, and "is not in his power, but in the power of destiny" (Spinoza, 2020: 225). Therefore, to overcome this passive state, Spinoza strongly advocated controlling emotion

under the guidance of reason. By acquiring distinct ideas concerning the nature of emotion and the relation between emotion and external causes, one can "have the power of ordering and concatenating the affections of the body according to the order of the intellect" (Spinoza, 2020: 297), thereby suppressing passionate emotion and sensual desires and becoming a free man. George Eliot deeply identifies with Spinoza's view, which is evident in her portrayal of the two female characters, Dorothea Brooke and Mary Garth.

1. Dorothea Brooke: Reason Overcoming Emotion

In the prelude of *Middlemarch*, Eliot highly praised the heroine Dorothea, comparing her to the sixteenth-century Christian Saint Theresa to highlight Dorothea's lofty ideological realm. Dorothea's "passionate, ideal nature demands an epic life" (Eliot, 2000: 3), and her greatest aspiration was to devote herself to society and achieve Theresa-like accomplishments. Moreover, she has also been trying to control her emotions with reason to achieve true freedom.

Although Dorothea's youth, ignorance, and blind fanaticism directly led to the failure of her first marriage, this setback prompted her to mature and realize that her marriage to Casaubon did not align with her aspirations. Simultaneously, she recognized the societal stereotypes regarding ideal marital partners for women: someone of the same age, a good match, or of higher status. However, Dorothea did not succumb to this societal pressure. Instead, with a profound understanding of herself, she defied others' opposition, followed her reason, resolutely abandoned Casaubon's inheritance, and chose to marry Will Ladislaw, with whom she shared a deep spiritual connection. This transition represented a shift from bondage to freedom on the level of oneself.

Many scholars interpreted Dorothea's decision to leave Lowick Manor and forsake her reputation, wealth, status, and family to be with the impoverished Will as a symbol of her transformation from a "firm and rare woman" to a "devoted wife and mother" (Yuan, 2012: 73). They argued that her return to the role of a

wife represents her surrender to reality, with her emotion overcoming her reason. The renowned British female writer Virginia Woolf even characterized this ending as a “compromise more depressing than tragedy” (ibid). However, their interpretations are not entirely accurate.

In fact, a deeper examination of Dorothea’s choice to be with Will reveals that they share similar ethical and moral beliefs, making their union entirely consonant with reason. Both of them possess a profound belief in moral perfection. Eliot repeatedly mentions Dorothea’s desire and aspiration for “goodness” and “the fullest truth”. In a conversation, Dorothea first expressed her life-defining belief: “That by desiring what is perfectly good, even when we don’t quite know what it is and cannot do what we would, we are part of the divine power against evil—widening the skirts of light and making the struggle with darkness narrower” (Eliot, 2000: 244). When Dorothea asked Will about his beliefs, his response concisely summarized his ethical perfectionism: “to love what is good and beautiful when I see it” (ibid). Their hearts thus align, as Dorothea remarked, “But if you like what is good, that comes to the same thing” (ibid). Therefore, for Dorothea, choosing Will against the weight of public opinion demonstrates her steadfastness in her beliefs.

The finale of the novel briefly depicts the marital life of Dorothea and Will, also revealing that Dorothea has not truly abandoned her ideals. “She never repented that she had given up position and fortune to marry Will Ladislaw” (Eliot, 2000: 513), and “she had now a life filled also with a beneficent activity which she had not the doubtful pains of discovering and marking out for herself” (ibid). Moreover, with her assistance, Will worked tirelessly and ultimately attained the position of a parliamentarian. Dorothea finds spiritual solace in assisting her husband’s career, indirectly fulfilling her lofty aspirations.

This conclusion illustrates that Dorothea’s choice to marry Will is a triumph of reason. She saw Will’s potential and believed that by supporting him, she could continue pursuing her

ideals and goals. Therefore, Dorothea achieved true freedom on the level of oneself. Through the portrayal of Dorothea, George Eliot not only inherits and develops Spinoza’s philosophical ideas regarding reason and emotion, freedom and bondage but also exhibits profound insight into the challenges faced by women in their pursuit of self-realization.

2. Mary Garth: Acting with Reason

Mary Garth, a woman who reins in her emotions, emerges as a paradigm of independent femininity in *Middlemarch*. Despite her plain appearance and humble origins, Mary eschewed the pursuit of power and refused to rely on marriage to elevate her social status. Unlike Dorothea’s idealism and Rosamond’s selfishness and vanity, Mary exhibited remarkable rationality and pragmatism, whether in pursuing her marital ideals or in reforming Fred Vincy.

Mary’s attitude towards love was unwavering, she never indulged her emotions. She and Fred Vincy, the son of the mayor of Middlemarch, have been childhood sweethearts. At six years old, Fred “espoused her with the umbrella ring” (Eliot, 2000: 322). Over the years, Mary has remained deeply in love with Fred, and she candidly told Reverend Farebrother “I will tell you that I have too strong a feeling for Fred to give him up for any one else. I should never be quite happy if I thought he was unhappy for the loss of me” (ibid). Even when she learned that the esteemed Reverend Farebrother had fallen in love with her, she did not rejoice excessively. Her reason told her that being with Fred was the right choice, thus she gently rejected the Reverend’s advances twice. This unwavering conviction ultimately brings her a happy marriage.

In addition, Mary’s rationality is also reflected in her firm rejection of Fred, who was unable to stand on her own in the early days. Fred is good-natured but weak in character, and due to the influence of his family environment and his mother’s over-indulgence, he is idle and even obsessed with gambling. He fantasized about relying on his uncle Mr. Featherstone’s inheritance for his future, rather than working for a living. Mary, however, viewed self-reliance

as the dignity of being human and expected her husband to live independently and assume family responsibilities as she did. Therefore, when Fred was still immature, she resolutely rejected his affection, preferring to remain unmarried, stating that “I will never engage myself to one who has no manly independence, and who goes on loitering away his time on the chance that others will provide for him” (Eliot, 2000: 163).

Mary’s transformation of Fred further demonstrates her reason and foresight. Although she desired Fred to have a legitimate profession and work diligently, she did not endorse his becoming a curate as a means of making a living. She knew this occupation was unsuitable for him, declaring that “I certainly never will be his wife if he becomes a clergyman” (Eliot, 2000: 321). It is her correct guidance that gradually steers this young man towards maturity, eradicating his vices and helping him discover his true interests. Fred ultimately became “distinguished in his side of the county as a theoretic and practical farmer” (Eliot, 2000: 521) and published a highly acclaimed book, *Cultivation of Green Crops and the Economy of Cattle-Feeding*, becoming the socially useful individual Mary envisioned.

Through the portrayal of Mary, George Eliot establishes a paradigm for women seeking social respect and a fulfilling family life. Simultaneously, Fred’s transformation reflects the significant role women play in reforming men. Mary’s success lies not only in her adherence to her inner convictions and love but also in her choice of a marriage that best aligns with her aspirations. She achieves true freedom, unmotivated by utilitarian goals but rather by her values and judgment. This freedom is what distinguishes her as more successful than other female characters in the novel.

Conclusion

By analyzing the concepts of freedom reflected in *Middlemarch* through three dimensions: man and nature, man and society, as well as man and self, readers can understand that the concepts of

freedom and restraint conveyed by Eliot in this novel are very consistent with Spinoza’s views in *Ethics*. Eliot masterfully crafts characters such as Celia Brooke, Dorothea Brooke, Nicholas Bulstrode, Tertius Lydgate, and Mary Garth to vividly illustrate the tortuous journey of pursuing freedom and the arduous challenges encountered in its realization. She not only inherits Spinoza’s views on freedom but also uniquely expands and deepens them.

Eliot firmly believes that under the guidance of reason, individuals must respect natural laws, abide by social norms, and overcome the constraints of their emotion to achieve true freedom and happiness. Their ideas not only provide valuable perspectives for understanding human freedom but also offer enlightening insights on how to achieve freedom and happiness in modern society.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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